

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

FROM THE PHYSICAL REALITY OF IMAGINARY NUMBERS IT FOLLOWS THAT THE INVISIBLE AFTERLIFE WORLD MENTIONED IN ALL RELIGIONS ACTUALLY PHYSICALLY EXISTS¹

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Abstract

The article proves that the generally accepted version of special theory relativity (SRT), which states that imaginary numbers are physically unreal, is incorrect. Experimental evidence is given of the general scientific principle of the physical reality of imaginary numbers, with the use of which a corrected version of the SRT was created. She argues that in addition to our visible universe, there are many other mutually invisible universes in nature. And they form the actually physically existing afterlife invisible world, predicted by all religions.

Keywords: imaginary numbers, special theory of relativity, invisible universes, afterlife invisible world

1. Introduction

Imaginary numbers, discovered about 500 years ago by Scipione Del Ferro, Niccolò Fontana Tartaglia, Gerolamo Cardano, Lodovico Ferrari and Raphael Bombelli [1], are known to everyone and are currently used in all exact sciences. They are even studied in school mathematics courses. But unlike other numbers that are understandable to everyone - integers and fractions, positive and negative, scalar and vector, etc. - their physical essence has not yet been explained. Indeed, what 2 kg., 3 m., 4 sec. is clear to everyone, but what is $2i$ kg., $3i$ m., $4i$ sec., where

$i = \sqrt{-1}$, no one can explain. Nevertheless, no one cared about this, just as, for example, now no one can explain. Nevertheless, no one cared about this, just as, for example, now no one cares that the phenomenon of ball lightning is not explained.

But at the beginning of the 20th century Joseph Larmor [2], Nobel Prize winner Hendrik Anton Lorenz [3], Jules Henri Poincaré [4], Nobel Prize winner Albert Einstein [5] and other outstanding scientists created the special theory of relativity, which rightly accepted to be considered an outstanding scientific achievement of physics of the 20th century, because it proposed the principle of relativity. And which is therefore now studied in all physics textbooks used in the educational process even at the most prestigious universities. However, in this theory, calculations using relativistic formulas, which were the final result of all reasoning, in some

cases led to a result measured by imaginary numbers. And this result already needed to be explained. After all, no one would need a theory that even its creators could not explain. But the authors of SRT did not know how to do this. And the fate of the service station hung in the balance. But it was saved by the fact that an additional postulate was introduced into the SRT, called the principle of not exceeding the speed of light, from which it followed that quantities measured by imaginary numbers do not exist in nature. And therefore, there is no need to explain them.

This is the form in which SRT is still taught.

2. The physical reality of imaginary numbers.

But besides STR there are other sciences. Including the theory of electrical circuits, which is used in radio engineering, electrical engineering and computer science. Fundamental to this theory is Ohm's law [6], [7], discovered in 1826 for DC electrical circuits, which is now studied even in school physics textbooks. And in 1893, Charles Proteus Steinmetz proposed its interpretation of Ohm's law for alternating current electrical circuits [8], which is now used daily by millions of engineers around the world in their work. In this theory of electrical circuits, the imaginary resistances of capacitors and inductors, which can be measured by instruments, were recognized as actually physically existing. And if these imaginary resistances were recognized as physically unreal, as follows from SRT, then neither radio engineering, nor electrical engineering, nor computers, nor radio measuring instruments should exist.

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Fig. 1. In any radio-technical laboratory there are devices called frequency response meters, which prove the physical reality of imaginary and complex numbers by their mere existence

But they do exist. And thereby they prove the physical reality of imaginary numbers [9]-[33]. Consequently, by the existence of radio- and electrical engineering, the generally accepted version of SRT was re-

futed even before its creation. Other proofs of the physical reality of imaginary numbers have been published in [34]-[46]. Therefore, the logical conclusion is that the version of STR currently presented in all physics textbooks is incorrect [47]-[66].

Fig. 2. Scheme of an astronomical experiment to detect invisible universes

3. Physical reality of invisible parallel universes

In the existing generally recognized version of SRT from its relativistic formulas and the principle of non-exceeding the speed of light also follows that in nature there is only our visible universe in which everything is measured only by real numbers.

However, in the corrected version of SRT [67]-[74], from its relativistic formulas it follows that in our Multiverse [75]-[85], in addition to our visible universe, there are also about twenty other mutually invisible parallel universes

And one can be convinced of their existence [86]-[91]. as a result of astronomical observations of the starry sky in portals [92]-[94], since the constellations in them will differ - and the further into the portal one penetrates, the greater the differences will be - from the constellations observed at the same time in the same region outside the portals. And since there are a lot of anomalous zones [95]-[98] on Earth, presumably being entrances to portals, some observatories have already are located in such anomalous zones. Like, for example, the main astronomical observatory of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, located in Golo-seyevsky forest 12 km from the center of Kyiv. Therefore, in order to verify the existence of neighboring invisible universes adjacent to our visible universe, it is

enough to compare on a computer the observations of this observatory with the observations of neighboring observatories located outside the anomalous zones.

4. Why, despite all the refutations of the generally accepted version of SRT, set out in all physics textbooks, it continues to be taught.

But this simple and low-cost experiment, which in the most indisputable way will allow us to answer the question of whether there are invisible universes neighboring our visible universe, no one has done or is going to do. Obviously, because physicists do not need such an answer, since it will refute the version of SRT studied in textbooks.

The corrected version of SRT states that imaginary numbers are physically real and invisible universes exist. Therefore, having become convinced of the existence of invisible universes, we will have to admit that the corrected version of SRT is correct and once again be convinced that imaginary numbers actually physically exist. And then it will inevitably be necessary to explain their physical meaning of imaginary numbers. And it is obvious - in addition to our visible world, there is an invisible world.

5. The existence of a physically real invisible world

However, the usefulness for science of the above experimental evidence of the physical reality of imaginary numbers goes beyond problems of correcting the version of SRT given in physics textbooks. From experimentally proven principle of the physical reality of imaginary numbers, one will inevitably have to conclude that the results of all studies described by imaginary numbers in all other exact sciences also are physically real.

Then many difficult questions will arise. For example, what exists in the looking glass when we see ourselves in the mirror? And therefore, in the end, we will have to admit that in addition to our visible world, there is also a huge (most likely even much larger than our visible world) invisible world [99]-[107]. Indeed, in addition to the room in which we are now and which we see, there are a large number of other invisible to us rooms in other apartments, houses, cities and countries. The same situation is in space – in addition to our visible universe, in other dimensions there are about twenty other parallel universes of the hidden Multiverse that are invisible to us. And outside of our hidden Multiverse in the Hyperverses, there are many other Multiverses.

And the existence of such a world invisible to us, in which Gods and the souls of the dead live, was long predicted by all world religions. Consequently, what these religions say about the world order, about the afterlife, is true. And therefore, all of us, the inhabitants of planet Earth, will now have to believe in this.

6. Conclusion

The author hopes that the information presented in the article will be an incentive to unite the efforts of science and religions in their activities for the benefit of people.

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